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Enhancing resilience in critical infrastructures through innovative pathways – The FIRELOGUE and STRATEGY projects approaches in emergency management

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Abstract

In cases of incidents impacting critical infrastructures, early notification and proper information sharing are vital for effective response and recovery. The EU 2557/2022 CER Directive outlines pathways to resilience, emphasizing the importance of coordinated efforts among Member States. The newly released CEN Workshop Agreement CWA 18024:2023 Emergency Management – Incident Situational Reporting for Critical Infrastructures provides a standardized approach for reporting incidents to national authorities, ensuring consistency and clarity in communication. Developed under the STRATEGY project, this CWA was rigorously tested in table-top and full-scale exercises with the participation of researchers, critical infrastructures operators and emergency responders. A pilot coordination center dedicated to critical infrastructures, utilizing a GIS-based platform from the Center for Security Studies (KEMEA) in Greece, facilitates seamless collaboration between critical entities and emergency responders during incidents that threaten the normal operation of these infrastructures. The (pre-) standardisation framework developed in STRATEGY was specifically designed to address the needs of emergency responders, ensuring that the CWA was tested across various scenarios to gain acceptance from a wide range of stakeholders. Moreover, in order to enhance situational awareness and to create a real-time common operational picture, an online incident reporting form, built on the CWA 18024:2023, has been integrated within the pilot coordination center. Undoubtedly, and during the tests, incident management was greatly improved leading to enhanced resilience of critical infrastructures. The FIRELOGUE workshops in 2023 (Solsona, Spain) and 2024 (Nea Makri, Greece) highlighted the critical role of technology in managing wildfires and their impact on infrastructures. Applications offering early warnings, fire ignition probabilities, and burnt area calculations are crucial for infrastructure operators and emergency responders. By combining data from various sources into a single, cohesive platform enhances the information's utility and management, allowing for more informed decision-making. Moreover, adherence to legislation and regulations is crucial for resilient infrastructures. The implementation of EU Directives not only strengthens resilience but also fosters a culture of preparedness and proactive risk management. In conclusion, effective incident management and collaboration are essential for the resilience of critical infrastructures. The integration of standardised reporting systems and technological advancements play a pivotal role in enhancing preparedness and response capabilities, ultimately safeguarding public safety and ensuring the continuity of essential services.

1. Introduction

Critical entities and their infrastructures are one of the key pillars of modern societies providing a broad spectrum of services to the population, from basic necessities such as access to clean water, electricity, telecommunication and heat to every household up to more sophisticated offerings like financial services, extremely fast internet services, cybersecurity, health services and other.

The European Union in an effort to enhance the resilience of infrastructures and make sure to provide a safe environment for their citizens, published out and put into act the Critical Entities Resilience Directive [1] and the NIS 2 Directive [2]. The Council CER Directive [1] broadens the concept of infrastructure by introducing the term "entity", and by including more types of infrastructures (i.e., banking, financial services, health services,

drinkingwater and water related services, digital infrastructures, production and distribution of food), besides the energy and transport sectors, compared to the previous Directive 114/2008 [3]. More precisely, it mandates a series of actions from the Member States to be implemented, such as, conducting risk assessment, continuous monitoring of the infrastructures, in real-time if possible, incident reporting, continuous collaboration and communication between infrastructures and state authorities. This will be achieved by each Member State by enlisting all their infrastructures that are compatible with the CER Directive [1] and by appointing a national contact point. The national contact point will be responsible to identify the national critical entities and will consist of the national authority that will perform all the functions and activities foreseen by the Directive in collaboration with all the necessary state authorities and other entities. As a follow up from this, STRATEGY project focused on addressing the requirements of critical entities and the authorities and developed the CWA 18024:2023 – Emergency management – Incident situational report [4].

Thus, a new era has begun in the critical infrastructure domain, which requires a continuous and close collaboration between all stakeholders and exchange of improved data in order to provide safe and secure services to the citizens. Unexpected events and/or incidents may be often inevitable, however the aim is to try to mitigate their impacts and limit the disruption of the service offered. Climate change can currently lead to extreme weather events and extreme and more frequent wildfires which may cause significant impact to the infrastructures. Other disruptive event, for which anticipation is necessary, is floods, which is a major threat for Europe, or the case of large earthquakes which occurrence is unavoidable.

In recent years, a significant attention has been given on wildfires, which is a typical threat for Southern Europe (Mediterranean countries) and emerging as a new concern for Central and Northern Europe. Moreover, extreme fire events, despite the reduction in the number of fires, occur more and more frequently in Southern Europe, with larger burnt areas, fast spread rates, high intensities, and megafires (e.g., [5]). EU under the Green Deal initiative has funded four Innovation Actions aimed to tackle wildfire challenges promoting an integrated approach and already the first results come up (e.g., [6], [7]).

Critical infrastructures play a crucial role in wildfire risk management, as they can act either as a triggering or ignition factor or as a suppression mechanism. The FIRELOGUE project and specifically the Infrastructure Working Group [8], which is a fundamental part of the project, is dealing with this issue.

2. Needs and challenges related to critical infrastructures and entities resilience

2.1 Enhancing crisis management in critical infrastructures through standardization - Insights from the STRATEGY project

A standard is a “document, established by consensus and approved by a recognized body, that provides, for common and repeated use, rules, guidelines or characteristics for activities or their results, aimed at the achievement of the optimum degree of order in a given context” [9]. The development of a standard consists of an open and ongoing procedure that incorporates the views, scientific and practical experience of subject matter experts. Critical infrastructures at national, even European and international level, benefit greatly of available standards, being part or not of the legal framework, due to their interconnected nature and services offered. In particular, crisis management within an infrastructure or disaster management at wider level when critical entities are involved, require the implementation of standardized actions and tools that facilitate cross-border and cross-organizational collaboration.

STRATEGY project developed a comprehensive, cross-European framework for pre-standardization activities related to systems, solutions, and procedures. This framework addresses crisis management and has been validated through the use of sustainable testing and evaluation frameworks. The overarching objective of the project, through the development and implementation of the pre-standardization activities, is to enhance the resilience of the EU in the face of a multitude of natural and man-made disasters through the assurance of first responder (FR) safety and the fortification of their operational capacity. In response to the identified needs of previous EU initiatives and the findings of the desktop research on EU priorities, the project addresses eight streams within the domain of crisis management. The following areas have been identified as requiring further

attention: Search and Rescue, Critical Infrastructure Protection, Response Planning, Command and Control, EarlyWarning Systems and Rapid Damage Assessment, CBRN-E, Training and Terminology.

The STRATEGY project following a desk research analysis on existing needs, challenges and gaps of emergency responders and practitioners, in the eight thematic topics stated previously, identified approximately 100 standardisation gaps on the field of crisis, and more specifically, on disaster management, among them being the protection of critical infrastructures ([10], [11]). The identified gaps in standardization related to critical infrastructures are the following:

- Definition of basic specifications and requirements for coordination centers of critical entities
- Specifications and requirements for equipment and space in coordination centres of CIs
- Standard DSS format of CI coordination centres.
- Standardised procedures for registration, authentication and authorisation of users in DSS and coordination centres systems.
- Post crisis needs assessment tools integrated to existing DSS.
- Interoperability between UAVs and DSS. Standardised data collection and mapping of UAVs, and transfer in the daily operations.
- Standardised intervention plans of first responders specifically for the CIP domain
- Processes and methods for dynamic risk evolution embedded in new and existing DSS (e.g., earthquake shaking, fire propagation, extreme weather forecasting). Requirements for standardized risk assessment modelling with an all-hazards approach, including climate change-related hazards.
- Standardised threat detection systems linked to DSS and coordination centres
- Cross-organisation interoperability with standardised data exchange formats, protocols and common SOPs, including security plans for interconnected CIs to enhance efficient information sharing and data sharing.

The analysis and discussions between practitioners, emergency responders and research partners of the project led to the development of two pre-standardisation items, two CEN Workshop Agreements:

- CWA 18024:2023 – Emergency management – Incident situational reporting for critical infrastructures [4].
- CWA 18028:2023 – Semantic layer definition and suitability of OASIS EDXL-CAP and OASIS EDXL-SitRep standards for crisis management in critical infrastructures [12].

These pre-standardisation items have been developed in collaboration with a broad spectrum of stakeholders and tested in one table-top (TTX) and one full-scale exercise (FSX) gathering feedback directly from the end users, i.e. the emergency responders the critical infrastructure operators, security liaison officers and all engaged stakeholders. The first one is discussed in more detail on chapter 3, as it consists of a new pre-standardisation item dedicated to support Member States in the implementation of the new EU CER Directive [1].

2.2 Enhancing Resilience: Integrated wildfire risk management and critical infrastructures protection

Wildfires, with increasing frequency and intensity, have become an event of major concern for policy makers and study focus of the scientific community. Recent disasters affecting critical infrastructures have provided evidence on the interdependencies between infrastructures, societal function and resilience in different dimensions (e.g. power outages in areas affected by wildfires and transport disruptions) [13]. Moreover, malfunctions in infrastructures can be a driving factor for wildfires, especially in the Wildland-Urban Interface

(WUI) (e.g., powerlines causing wildfires). As a matter of fact, there is a mutual cause-effect relationship between wildfires and infrastructures, the understanding of which can lead to the adoption of efficient risk reduction measures and impactful actions:

- **Infrastructure as a driving factor in fire regime.** Infrastructure's malfunction, failure or misuse may lead to wildfire ignition. Prevention measures for the assets upgrade and/or vegetation management of the surrounding areas are deemed necessary. Additionally, the positive involvement of different infrastructures in wildfire management should be further exploited (e.g., role of road network as fire break).
- **Impact of wildfires to infrastructure.** Wildfires can adversely affect the operation of infrastructure assets and networks exposed due to their geographic location, causing disruption of the service provided. This tendency has increased due to the expansion of human settlements and industrial activity into the wildland.
- **Cross-cutting topics** are also evident, such as (i) the nature-based solutions infrastructures may adopt for their protection against wildfires; (ii) the necessary societal awareness and preparedness in case of an emergency caused by service disruption; (iii) the insurance claims in case of an infrastructure-ignited fire and vice versa; (iv) the role of civil protection agencies in ensuring resilience planning and emergency training on behalf of critical infrastructure operators, (v) climate change projections and EU climate change adaptation policies regarding infrastructures and WFRM.

In this respect, the working group Infrastructure of FIRELOGUE project generated insights and recommendations on the abovementioned topics, lying under the overarching theme of the interaction of infrastructure with its surrounding natural environment and their exposure to wildfires. The FIRELOGUE project is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) granted under the Horizon 2020 Green Deal programme (H2020-LC-GD-1-1) on preventing and managing extreme wildfire events through the integration and demonstration of innovative tools and means [8]. The objective of the project is to facilitate a discourse and empower the Wildfire Risk Management (WFRM) community to address both current and future wildfire challenges. FIRELOGUE brings together various types of stakeholders in order to discuss and improve WFRM. It is structured into five working groups focused on: i) the environment, ii) society, iii) infrastructures, iv) insurance and v) civil protection, which allow discussions across four thematic strands: socio-economic, climate change mitigation, technology and earth observation, in order to promote policies that support wildfire risk management.

FIRELOGUE examines the co-existence of wildfires and critical infrastructures in a participatory method and a dialogue between the various engaged stakeholders. Following a series of extended experts discussions, it has been pointed out there is a need to follow a more integrated approach with a stronger collaboration between involved stakeholders and improved data exchange. A lack in risk assessment is evident as in the use of modern technologies, while a prioritization towards research is necessary. Strengthening of infrastructures against wildfires is also necessary [14].

The preliminary recommendations findings [14] of the dialogue that Firelogue are focused on the collaboration and coordination among the governmental agencies, private sector and communities; enhancing the collaboration among infrastructures, improved data sharing, support training, invest more in research and technology, conduct risk assessment following the mandates of the CER directive, move towards real-time estimations, implement risk management at various levels, considering the landscape, enhance standardisation and implement a cultural change towards prevention, mitigation and preparedness, engaging the community.

It has to be noted that these recommendations do not simply represent wildfire risk management issues related to critical infrastructures. Instead, some of these must be considered as recommendations to improve the emergency management system which accounts for various risk types (natural and man-made) and not only wildfire prevention, response and recovery.

3. Enhancing incident situational reporting: A pre-standard for critical infrastructures supporting the implementation of the CER Directive

3.1 The CWA 18024:2023 – Brief overview

The CER Directive [1] through its 15th article mandates all Member States to ensure that all critical entities notify on time, without undue delay, and the latest, no later than 24 hours, the competent authority of incidents that disrupt significantly the provision of essential services. Moreover, CER Directive [1] asks for a detailed report, submitted no later than one month after the incident. In addition, the minimum incident notification should include information about the number and proportion of users affected, the duration of the disruption, and the geographical area affected. Finally, the CER directive [1] asks for the notification of the Commission in case the incident has an impact on six or more Member States.

CWA 18024:2023 [4] is a CEN Workshop Agreement document that provides a common set of information, terms and datatypes as requirements and recommendations that should be made available to a national, local or European coordination centre, control room, contact point or any competent authority, by any affected critical infrastructure in case of an incident. It consists of a set of information that mainly targets the higher command levels, at strategic and operational level [15] but not aimed at the tactical forces on the scene. This set of requirements and recommendations can fully support Member States in the implementation of the EU CER Directive, being compatible with the “Article 15 – Incident notification”.

The information that is requested to be filled in by the user is categorised in four main pillars:

- the identification of the user and the incident,
- the description of the incident, in simple words structured description of what happened,
- the characterization of the impacts and the risk in a structured way,
- additional information about the actions in place and resources needed to face the incident and restore the service.

Practically, the pre-standard is structured in a way that provides to coordination centres all the necessary information to estimate the current situation, provide the future evolution of the incident and help them to understand what resources may be needed. This is done in a sequence, and it is assumed that at least four types of reports exist: the initial report, an update, a final report and a cancellation report, indicating the closing of the emergency. The CWA has been built in such a way to take into account technological systems, meaning that its implementation facilitates the use of technological system, and it can be used in a typical paper format or a modern technological system.

All the information requested by the CER directive has been covered, as the user preparing the report, i.e., the critical infrastructure operator, can provide information about themselves, the incident, the geographical area, in the form of geographical coordinates with a polygon, access to the area, details on the incident, the impacts, the restoration time objective, the number of people expected to be affected, what actions have been made or will be made and what potential resources may be needed. The end user has the freedom to fill in any information and update it at any time it is necessary to do so, and they are instructed always to provide the best possible estimation. Nevertheless, at the final report, the recommendation is to provide the real numbers and not estimations.

Thus, the proposed standardized incident reporting form facilitates the collaboration between critical entities and emergency response services, it provides an enhanced situational awareness and common operational picture, and a common language to the involved stakeholders in an easy-to-understand and -to-use format. Moreover, it can be employed by competent authorities to create statistics, as it can be used for any type of incident, of higher or lower severity, natural or man-made, for any type of infrastructure including infrastructure in the food and feed sector and help on future improvements. Finally, it is compatible with other similar standards used outside Europe such as the [16] in UK, the [17] and the [18].

3.2 Collaborative validation at operational level using modern technological applications

The CWA 18024:2023 [4] was developed in collaboration with the end-users, emergency responders and critical infrastructure operators, with their active participation, not only for the development of the document, but also during table-top and full-scale exercises. The latter activities, i.e. the exercises were the main validation tool of the under-development standards in the framework of STRATEGY project. An innovative, end-user driven pre-standardization framework that facilitated the development of new standards in crisis management domain, or the improvement of existing ones was developed in STRATEGY.

It was tested in one TTX that was organized at the premises of Center for Security Studies (KEMEA), in Athens, Greece in June 2022 and a FSX and demonstration, as part of a larger scenario, that took place in the area of Gualdo-Tadino and Valfabbrica in Italy (March 2023). These exercises were not used for training of the involved personnel, although they facilitate such purpose, but to test the standards, to evaluate and validate whether the standards can fit to existing operational procedures and meet the needs of FRs. In these two exercises, the CWA [4] was tested in different scenarios with the use of modern technological systems. The implementation of the exercises was based upon the eXercise Guidance Method - XGM framework [19] developed in the STRATEGY project. XGM is a reference framework on conducting exercises for standards and it is based on the Trial Guidance Methodology-TGM [20]. Thus, for each exercise, at least one person was assigned for each of the following roles: the exercise manager, the problem owner, the research leader, the host and the technical support leader.

In the first case, the TTX, both natural and man-made independent events were selected without an escalation difficulty as this was the first real test with the end users. The tests included three different incidents affecting critical infrastructures, one large earthquake affecting a metropolitan area with the focus given on the damage of a main natural gas pipeline, the second event included a man-made incident, an emergency landing of an airplane that ended to be a highjack and the third episode was related to an overturn of a truck carrying hazardous chemical materials along a main highway.

The FSX was based on two different scenarios, the first one was related to an earthquake and the collapse of a nearby dam (scenario A), and the second one was related to a wildland urban interface fire (scenario B), testing in total 14 standardization items (CEN Workshop Agreements and Technical Specifications). CWA 18024:2023 [4] was tested with the first scenario. A large earthquake occurred in the location area hitting a water reservoir. The reservoir even though was designed to withstand a large earthquake, a new section being under test load was affected, leading to its partial collapse, generating a water wave that escaped the overflow channel and poured into the riverbed. The nearby highway was flooded as well as a stadium full of people. During the exercise, in the command centre, the end users (emergency responders and civil protection authorities) were receiving the various relevant information, through the incident form which was filled in by the local infrastructure operators.

The infrastructure operators with the use of an online form built in ArcGIS Survey 123, which is an online representation of the [4], reported the incident to the command centre and the national competent authority (Figure 1). The report is being translated into a web-GIS environment and the same picture is shared among all involved stakeholders.

Figure 1. Left: online form for incident reporting according to CWA 18024:2023 [4]. Right: Indicative screenshot for the KEMEA risk application and incident report built for the full-scale exercise that was carried out in Italy.

Source: Left: <https://survey123.arcgis.com/share/35a360a8d90249a998ea59997867e0db>. Right: Ruiz and Sakkas [21].

The use of modern Geographic Information Systems (GIS) allows all the necessary information to be translated into a map view, thus making it easier to communicate and understand the information. Moreover, during both exercises, besides the testing of the pre-standardisation items, the integration and interoperability of various systems was also examined and tested. In Figure 2, the technical setup and the integration of the various technological systems is also presented, from the end user online form and front end to the KEMEA's ArcGIS sever and to STRATEGY's project testbed. Finally, in Figure 3, an example of the printed output of the incident report based on the recommendations of the CWA 18024:2023 [4] is presented as being presented in the FSX. These recommendations, provided in CWA 18024:2023 [4] have taken into account various options in order to suggest a template that will provide to the reader the most important information, such as the severity of the incident and its impacts with a catch of the naked eye without devoting significant time for reading it.

Figure 2. Integration schema used both in the TTX and FSX.

Source: Ruiz and Sakkas [21].

Figure 3. Indicative example of a recommended printed format (CWA 18024:2023, [4]) from an incident as presented in theFSX.

INCIDENT REPORT (CWA – Emergency Management – Incident situational Reporting) FSX - 30 March 2023					
User and incident identifier					
Incident Report type	Incident ID	Linked incident	Linked incident ID	CI Business name	
Report	201	0	0	Valfabbrica Dam	
Incident Creation Date/Time (Local)	Report recipients	CI Sector	Person or group reporting		Person authorized
3/29/2023 13:10	Fire_Service,Medical_emergency_services,Civil_protection,Police_authorities,other	Water - reservoir	Dam security team		Dam security officer
Contact email	Contact tel	+00	Country (code)	IT	
valdam@valfabbrica-dam.it					
Incident basic information description					
Incident type			Incident severity		
True incident			HighlyConfident		
Incident Occurrence Date/Time (local)	Area	Latitude (WGS84)	Longitude (WGS84)	Elevation (m)	Radius
3/30/23 7:05 AM	Valfabbrica area				
Incident description	Due to the earthquake a leak from the dam was observed which led to a dam partial collapse. The integrity of the dam has been seriously affected. Areas to the downstream of the dam are expected to be flooded.				
Accessibility status	Not yet known. Main roads may be flooded. Suggestion to use alternative access of higher altitudes.				
Incident hazard and impacts					
Hazard type	Incident severity a)	Incident urgency a)	Incident priority a)		
De collapse due to earthquake	Extreme	Immediate	Extremely critical priority / 4		
Impact description	Scale of impacts				
The dam has collapsed partially and its stability has been affected. Collapse may be expanded. Waters run already downstream with the risk to flood the areas below the dam (Valfabbrica, stadium and houses).	Unknown / 0				
CI Service affected	Human losses	Expected external impacts (to other CIs)	Other CI sector affected		Restoration time

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INCIDENT REPORT (CWA – Emergency Management – Incident situational Reporting) FSX - 30 March 2023					
Water supply stopped.	Unknown	Unknown. Maybe the road has been flooded.	Water supply stopped.	Unknown.	
Actions					
Actions in place			Alternative infrastructure for service provision		
Yes			Not applicable		
Description of the actions	0				
Resources					
Resources used by the CI					
0					

Source: Ruiz and Sakkas [21].

4. Discussion and Conclusions

Critical entities, their protection and resilience are crucial in modern societies. Any incident, man-made or natural, that may affect a specific critical infrastructure can have significant impact to the society and may trigger cascading effects to other critical infrastructures or entities. The stability and well-being of the society rely on uninterrupted essential services. The European Commission with the publishing of the two new Directives

[1] and [2] clearly aims to a more holistic approach that will support the enhancement of the resilience of the critical entities towards a safer European Union for its citizens.

The findings from the STRATEGY project in the CIP domain point out a clear need for improved collaboration among involved stakeholders. Faster diffusion of standardised exchange of data and information, a common operational picture and situation awareness, standardised risk assessment and processes, as well as dynamic risk evolution are crucial. Use of modern technological systems such as command and control centres, UAVs, and DSS are vital with a focus on standardisation and interoperability between the systems being a key factor.

The recent findings of FIRELOGUE project also support the work of STRATEGY project in the CIP domain, focusing on wildfire risk management. Current needs in wildfire risk management relevant to infrastructures point out the lack of collaboration among stakeholders in wildfire management, global support for decision-makers, and enforcement of legal frameworks at Member State level, contribution to insufficient data sharing and cooperation. Advanced monitoring technologies are limited, and training programs are inadequate. Real-time risk assessment capabilities are lacking, and continuous training for first responders is also insufficient. There is also a lack of standardized data-sharing protocols and little knowledge available about fire prevention technologies, socio-economic impacts, and further operational elaboration on the findings of integrated fire risk modeling. The importance of understanding exposure analysis, building resilience in structures, addressing gaps in current codes, implementing strategies to mitigate risks, leveraging agroforestry systems, using standardized data schemas, accurately defining exposure, and focusing on hazard identification and mitigation. Overall, enhancing resilience in critical infrastructures is essential in mitigating societal impacts. Collaborative efforts and technological advancements are key in building a safer environment for all citizens.

The main scope of this document is aimed at improving the resilience of critical infrastructures and mitigating risks following a holistic approach, considering the interconnectivity of various critical infrastructures. Enhanced resilience requires standardized procedures, widely accepted by all the types of stakeholders. Codes, norms and legislation are an important guide for this path. Technology offers innovative tools to make things simpler, faster and interoperable. Modern technological tools offer significant advantages in continuous monitoring, early warning and detection. Technological advancements also offer important tools that can support the response phase of an incident, especially providing real-time situation awareness and common operational picture to all involved stakeholders. Last but not least, technology can support the use of standards as well as can promote new materials and services compatible with standardized procedures.

The combination of a standard with a technological tool in a simulation environment (table-top) and field exercise in the STRATEGY project clearly showcased a positive outcome of using technology in the daily work of emergency response services and infrastructures, and it was positively accepted by end-users. However, successful implementation requires system readiness and political will to embrace these changes. The participatory process in the STRATEGY project and FIRELOGUE project clearly highlights that responders and infrastructures are ready and available to use new technologies following standardized protocols in order to facilitate their work and guarantee a safer society. This proactive approach reflects an understanding of the need for innovation in response to evolving challenges.

A recent, good example of modern technology to combat wildfires in action is observed in Greece, particularly following the devastating wildfires of 2023. The current deployment of permanent patrolling UAVs has revolutionized early detection and warning systems, enabling rapid response to wildfires. While these technologies do not guarantee complete success in fire suppression, they represent a crucial step toward addressing incidents in their early stages. The political will to integrate such technological tools signifies an acknowledgment of current professional needs and priorities. The use of various sensors and new technological tools (UAVs, satellites, local sensors, weather sensors) is starting to become a prerequisite in order to gather data and acquire more information on the incident [22, 23], potentially affecting a critical infrastructure. Nevertheless, this does not mean that one size fits all solutions, but it is certainly a step towards improved resilience.

Another good example of the use of technology in the critical infrastructure domain is the study of [24] who conducted a computer assisted exercise (CAX) in Greece, which aimed to bring together operators of critical infrastructures and emergency responders. This exercise successfully identified possible civil protection system inconsistencies and provided practical recommendations for strengthening information exchange and cooperation among infrastructure operators, eventually enhancing infrastructure and societal resilience. Players evaluated positively the technological tools used during the drill, emphasizing the benefits of direct information exchange and standardized reporting, both during training and real-life operations.

Another example of political will to incorporate new technologies in disaster risk management and specifically on wildfires is the recent peer review assessment of the Union Civil Protection Mechanism on wildfires [25]. This evaluation emphasizes the importance of utilizing state-of-the-art technologies to safeguard lives, environment, and properties. It also promotes environmentally friendly, sustainable civil protection activities as part of a comprehensive resilience approach. Italy, for example, stands out as a model, having implemented technological enhancements following the 2021 wildfires, focusing on prevention, prediction, and swift action.

The combination of research and innovation, along with standardization, regulations, and political determination, establishes a strong foundation for developing resilient critical entities and infrastructure. By prioritizing these factors, societies can create secure pathways toward improved preparedness and response capabilities in the face of evolving threats.

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List of abbreviations and definitions

CAX	Computer Assisted Exercise
CWA	CEN Workshop Agreement
CIP	Critical Infrastructure Protection
DSS	Decision Support System
FR(s)	First responder(s)
FSX	Full Scale Exercise
TGM	Trial Guidance Methodology
TTX	Table-top Exercise
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
WFRM	Wildfire Risk Management
WUI	Wildland Urban Interface
XGM	eXercise Guidance Method